

NEXT STEPS IN DEVELOPING AN OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE (OSI)

PROGRAMME PLAN SPII-2

Version 0.4; 12 June 2026

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MANAGEMENT SUMMARY

SPII-2 is set up as a co-production programme, involving key stakeholders from research institutions, infrastructure providers and national initiatives. The programme is structured along five interrelated lines of approach:

- [A] Development of additional use cases, potentially leading to additional requirements for OSI
- [B] Technical setup – developing a reference model and interoperability requirements
- [C] Connecting and collaborating with infrastructures (existing and in development)
- [D] Scenarios for a business model
- [E] Explorative studies potentially affecting OSI (AI, decentralisation)

These lines are strongly interdependent and will be coordinated and integrated by a core group.

This programme plan is in development and will be updated periodically to reflect discussions with the various stakeholders:

- In version 0.4 the descriptions of lines B and C have been revised
- In an additional chapter (Chapter 6. Scope for 2026) the activities foreseen for 2026 are described.

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1. OBJECTIVES OF SPII-2

DESIRED RESULTS

Building on the results of SPII-1, SPII-2 has the following objectives:

1. **Development of the Reference Model Open Science Infrastructure:** The Reference model describes the reference architecture for the federated infrastructure, the connections between the participating infrastructural elements and the technical, semantic and legal agreements/definitions that underpin the federated infrastructure.
2. **Developing additional use-cases:** SPII-1 has been developed based on 12 use-cases. Under supervision of the SPII-2 programme, additional use-cases will be developed – with different perspectives and/or different domains – in order to see if these will lead to additional requirements for the reference model.
3. **Connection and collaboration with ongoing infrastructural development projects:** From 2026 onwards, a number of infrastructural projects financed by OSNL and others such as TDCC, are developing open science infrastructural elements. SPII-2 connects and collaborates with these projects as well as existing infrastructure with the aim of informing and shaping the reference model.
4. **Connection with EOSC:** EOSC is the European ‘federation of federations’. OSI will work with EOSC-NL in order to ensure a good fit with the developing EOSC infrastructure.
5. **Roadmap for Open Science infrastructure 2027-2031:** Proposal for a timeline to implement OSI.
6. **Governance, organisation and finances:** Developing different scenarios (minimal, intermediate, advanced) for the governance, organisation and finances in order to maintain and develop the Open Science Infrastructure.

STAKEHOLDERS ON BOARD

Another important objective of the SPII-2 programme is to ensure that the OSI developments are understood, discussed and supported by the stakeholders. In other words, the process is as important as the results.

GLOBAL TIMELINE

- The present programme plan describes the activities for the calendar year 2026.
- Interim results will be reported in December 2026.
- It is foreseen that to fully attain the above-described objectives, the SPII-2 programme will also run in 2027. To this end, a conference planned for 10 February 2027, will be held to discuss the interim results with the stakeholders and to plot the next steps for the development of OSI.

2. BUILDING ON SPII-1

A brief overview of the results of SPII-1 ^{1,2}:

- OSI (Open Science Infrastructure) is positioned as the Open Science perspective on the broader digital research infrastructure.
- The development method was based on 12 use-cases related to FAIR sharing of research results. For each use-case, the necessary technical elements were identified, including which of these should be federated. In addition, the social and human elements and the federated agreements regarding standards and interoperability were identified.
- OSI builds on existing digital research infrastructural elements/modules as much as possible. A few missing infrastructural elements have been identified for OSI to function as a whole. Since the publication of the SPII-1 report mid-2025, a number of infrastructural projects have started to develop some of these missing elements.
- A federated, modular design has been chosen as the starting point to align as closely as possible with existing systems.
- FAIR sharing of research results at the workflow level of researchers and research supporting professionals is seen as the main function of OSI and is simultaneously its main business case.
- When the OSI-infrastructure functions as a federated system, it will have the following additional functions:
 - Visibility and dissemination of Dutch research results
 - Monitoring of system usage via counters and metrics
 - Open Research Information collected from the various infrastructural elements
 - Archiving and long-term preservation of Dutch research results.
- Development of OSI should contribute to digital sovereignty and sustainability.

Figure 1 Overview OSI [SPII-1]

3. SETUP SPII-2

3.1 CO-PRODUCTION WITH STAKEHOLDERS

SPII-1 was set up as a project with a project group, a Steering Committee and an Advisory Board. Consultation with the various stakeholders took place on the basis of an interim report.

The proposal is to structure SPII-2 as a programme with co-production with the stakeholders as its guiding principle. A sketch of this setup with potential working methods is presented in figure 2.

Figure 2 Sketch co-production with stakeholders

3.2 STEERING COMMITTEE AND CORE GROUP COMPOSITION

Steering Group	
Name	Organisation
Darco Jansen	UNL
John Doove	SURF
Frans Oort	UvA
Sarah Coombs	Association of Universities of Applied Sciences

Core group	
Name	Organisation
Till Bey	SURF
Maurice Vanderfeesten	SURF
Jason Maassen	eScience Centre

Marcel Ras	UNL-VU
Patris van Boxel	DANS
Bolinda Hoeksema	SHB
Joost Elshof	VH
Louise Bezuidenhout	CWTS
Josefien Schuurman	Bibliotheek UvA/HvA
Sander Bosch	UNL-VU
Nida van Leersum	Build to Impact; programme co-lead
Maurits van der Graaf	Pleiade; programme co-lead

4. FIVE LINES OF APPROACH

4.1 INTRODUCTION

FIVE LINES OF APPROACH

-
- (A) Additional use-cases [potentially leading to additional requirements for OSI]
 - (B) Technical set-up – developing a reference model and interoperability requirements]
 - [C] Connecting and collaborating with infrastructures (existing and in development)
 - [D] Organisational set-up (several scenarios)
 - [E] Explorative studies potentially affecting OSI [AI & decentralisation]

Figure 3 Five lines of approach

Five lines of approach for the SPII-2 programme have been developed, based on the feedback that was received to the SPII-1 report.

Each line of approach requires a different setup. In the next paragraphs, the five lines of approach are described with suggestions for the approach to be taken. This is a dynamic programme plan, and the approaches per line might be adapted as a result of the engagement with the stakeholders.

COORDINATING AND CONNECTING THE FIVE LINES

The main tasks of the core group are:

- (1) Set up and monitor the progress of the five lines of approach
- (2) Initiate, coordinate, and report on the five lines of approach, as the five lines are strongly interdependent.

[A] DEVELOPMENT OF ADDITIONAL USE-CASES

WHAT?

Potential use-cases to be developed (suggested in the feedback to SPII-1):

- New domains: Citizen Science, OER/Open Education, monographs, micropublications, research protocols, ‘publishing containers’; ‘research compendiums/knowledge stack’
- New perspectives: STM and SSH disciplines; research group leader/ research institute
- Execution phase of research cycle/ research tools of various disciplines.

WHY?

To see if these use-cases lead to additional requirements for OSI while simultaneously these use-cases will lead to a better understanding of how these workflows connect with OSI

HOW?

Who?

- Engaging stakeholders & communities to develop use-cases that are relevant to them

How?

- Using various methods to engage stakeholders (direct approach, more generic approach)
- Supported by written instruction on the SPII-1 method

Planning: to be developed.

[B] TECHNICAL SET-UP – DEVELOPING A REFERENCE MODEL AND INTEROPERABILITY REQUIREMENTS

WHAT?

The aim is to develop a reference model for infrastructure elements that wish to participate in the federated open science infrastructure. Such a reference model – somewhat similar to the OAIS reference model for archiving – makes clear what infrastructure elements should do to become part of the federated infrastructure. Participation should be beneficial both for the infrastructure element itself and for the federation as a whole. ‘A Lego brick that clicks into place within the federative infrastructure’.

The reference model includes:

- Guiding principles and values
- Shared terminology
- High-level sketch
- Interoperability framework including technical, semantic, legal and organisational agreements

Among the activities in this line of approach, the following seems important:

- Review developments at NFDI³⁻⁵, Finland^{6,7}, [OStrails](#), and other initiatives.
- Ensure alignment with:
 - Connection to EOSC (technical aspects)
 - HORA/HOSA reference infrastructure for researchers is being updated. The OSI reference model should align with it.
 - The CIOs are developing a digital strategy for 2035 (UNL assignment); UNL will have from the summer 2026 a policymaker for digital infrastructures who can help.

WHY A REFERENCE MODEL?

1. basis for working together

- a common language
- identify areas of collaboration
- reuse solution patterns
- who works on what?

2. support development

- mapping of existing state
- identify gaps and opportunities
- steering towards goal state

3. tool for impact analysis

- exposure to risks
- consequences of decision
- uncover dependencies

HOW?

- An iterative process (to be developed further with the stakeholders) is foreseen with:
 - A development group with software architects and IT-savvy professionals (n=6) that works out in steps elements of the reference model
 - A wider consultation of reviewers among stakeholders (especially the OSNL infrastructural projects and existing research infrastructures) that reviews each interim result proposed by the development group.
- Experiences and results from other countries will be included in the process: there are similar projects in Germany (NFDI), Finland and possibly other countries (see the references mentioned above).
- A more detailed proposal for the working method (a small and lightweight subsection of HORA) is in development (see Appendix 1)

[C] CONNECTING AND COLLABORATING WITH INFRASTRUCTURES (EXISTING AND IN DEVELOPMENT)

WHAT?

As stated above, in SPII-1 several infrastructural elements were identified that were considered as essential for OSI and were missing at the moment of writing. However, a number of infrastructural projects have since started to develop these and other elements (e.g. the OSNL projects awarded in 2025 and TDCC projects). In addition, there are existing infrastructures that are relevant to OSI.

In the table below, the description per ‘missing’ infrastructural components of the SPII-1 report is repeated (current situation, objective and the proposed solution) and some of the most relevant development projects are listed. However, as mentioned before, there are other development projects, as well as existing infrastructures, that are facilitating open science and thus relevant for open science infrastructure.

Research administration
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current situation: Researchers are faced with increasing administrative obligations (DMP, ethics, GDPR, licences) at the start of a research project. Several institutions are currently developing a system to support researchers’ workflows and avoid redundant data entry. • Objective: End-to-end integration of Open Science-related metadata throughout the duration of the research project
Relevant infrastructural development projects:

Several institutional research administration development projects: research management portal at the UvA, similar projects at faculties of the RUG etc.
Current situation: CRIS/repositories set up for registration and reporting. Widely differing working methods, considerable duplication of effort
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Optimisation and harmonisation CRIS/repositories 2. Publication channel for workflows for (innovative) publication formats.
Relevant infrastructural development projects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DURF, Diamond, PRC model, MORIS, and other OSNL projects (see appendix 4). • The international development project around Open Research Europe (renewal of the infrastructure making it into a platform for the PRC model as well as Diamond journal publishing) • OpenAIRE developments • COAR initiatives
Research data infrastructure
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current situation: • Wide variety of RDM infrastructure components; undergoing rapid development • Virtually no integration between research administration → data management plan → data management environment → (long-term) data repository • Lack of automated data access mechanisms for datasets with access restricted by conditions. • Objectives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ End-to-end integration where possible through federation ○ Automation where possible to reduce the burden on researchers
Relevant infrastructural development projects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Yoda project and other OSNL projects (see appendix 4) ▪ UvA projects: Research Hub/FAIR Data hub⁸ (MPV to be delivered soon), RDX (Research Data Exchange), ▪ SURF: Data Access Broker
Sharing and reusing research software infrastructure
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current situation: With Research Software Directory several years ago, the technical components are in place for the sharing and reuse of research software. However, adoption remains low. • Objectives: To promote the adoption of sharing and reusing research software by developing widely supported Best Practices.
Relevant infrastructural development projects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ RSD project ▪ other OSNL projects (see appendix 4)
Open research information, discovery and active dissemination
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current situation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Some research information is not open, other information is fragmentedly available. ○ Discovery and dissemination via the Netherlands Research Portal have gaps in functionality • Objectives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Research information as complete as possible and openly available ○ Improved discovery and dissemination of Dutch research output
Relevant infrastructural development projects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Broccoli project ▪ MORIS, PubliNova, Sharekit ▪ PID-to-portal, ORI at SURF ▪ other OSNL projects (see appendix 4) ▪ OpenAire ▪ OpenAlex

Table 1 Infrastructural components needed for OSI and relevant development projects [in blue: contact person in core group SPII-2]

Other OS infrastructural projects: SPII-2 will need to connect with a number of other OSNL infrastructural projects developing open science modules (see appendix 4). This includes projects that develop an open science research tool.

WHY?

Working together with these projects and existing infrastructures will inform and shape the reference model for open science infrastructure.

HOW?

This line will be closely coordinated with line [B] Technical setup - development of the reference model. There is already the 'koppelvlakkenoverleg' where the OSNL projects on PRC, Diamond, DURF and Broccoli and other projects such as ORI, Pid-to-portal, MORIS, WijsNL periodically meet. A suggestion to enlarge this meeting with some other projects that are closely connected to the OSI (such as Yoda, RSD, Research Hub) is under discussion.

With regard to the other OSNL projects and other relevant infrastructural projects, a conference to be organised on July 1 will be a starting point for engagement and collaboration. The benefit for OSI as well as these projects is that – if the resulting infrastructural elements become a functional part of the federated model of OSI – they can also become part of the organisation of the federation if Line [D] regarding the organisational setup of the federation will be successful.

See Appendix 2 for the first outlines of a potential working method.

[D] ORGANISATIONAL SETUP FOR OSI (SEVERAL SCENARIOS)

WHAT?

- Governance, organisation, finances/business model
- Roadmap implementation
- Connection to other infrastructural elements (GWI, EOSC) (organisational aspects)

WHY?

To pave the way for the implementation of the infrastructure for Open Science

HOW?

For this line of approach, the GORC-model is proposed as a reference model (see figure 3). Proposals need to be developed for the white boxes in the figure that are related to the federated modules and the federated interoperability agreements. In other words: the scope is on the costs, governance and engagement of the stakeholders regarding the elements and agreements that maintain the federated infrastructure (outside scope: the modules that are 'being federated'). Priorities for:

- Financial sustainability
- Governance structures
- Stakeholder engagement.

Key issues are:

- **Costs of implementation and maintenance:** It is crucially important to create an early and realistic understanding of the costs of the implementation (CAPEX) and maintenance (OPEX) of OSI. In previous development projects, cost calculations were made only

after development. This led to outcomes being perceived as prohibitively expensive by governing boards. Therefore, in this programme, cost modelling should take place in parallel with the design and development of OSI, using several scenarios (minimal, intermediate, advanced).

- **Organisation and governance:** It is anticipated that the maintenance of the federative infrastructure for OSI will require a form of organisation that handles day-to-day management and further developments. In addition, OSI needs a governance structure that aligns with existing governance structures for research and research infrastructures.

A possible approach for this line could be:

1. **Cost building blocks:** Identification of cost building blocks for federated modules/federating elements and services (development and operation) that are needed for the federated infrastructure of OSI. It is also important to estimate the potentially additional costs for an infrastructural element/module to participate in the federated infrastructure.
2. **References and benchmarks:** References of development and operational costs for existing, similar systems such as repositories, CRIS systems, AAI systems and portals/aggregation platforms.
3. **Scenarios:** Developing several scenarios for maturity of the earlier identified cost building blocks (for example regarding the extent of integration in the federative infrastructure).

There are several other projects in 2026 that are working on governance and organisational requirements for shared infrastructures among research performing organisations. The result of these projects will be known in the autumn of 2026. The proposal is to develop in November a few scenarios for business models building on the results of the aforementioned projects (see also chapter 6).

Figure 4 GORC model

[E] EXPLORATIVE STUDY

WHAT?

- Identify the possible effects of new technological developments (decentralized models; AI agents, ...).

WHY?

- Recent technological developments regarding decentralised models and AI agents might revolutionise the architecture of existing IT-infrastructures.

HOW?

Who?/how:

- Brainstorming sessions with experts in these fields:
 - First brainstorming session at the first stages of the development of OSI to see if the above-mentioned technological developments can already influence the direction of architecture development.
 - Second brainstorming session in the final stages of the development of OSI to see if certain elements of the proposed OSI implementation need to be adjusted as a result of these technological developments.

Planning:

- As in 2026, the focus will lie on the reference model that might be translated in a later phase to a concrete technical setup, these explorative studies will be relevant at that moment and are for the moment postponed to that later stage.

5. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT^a AND COMMUNICATION

5.1 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

Figure 5 Co-production with stakeholders

In figure 5 several options for co-production with stakeholders and communities are depicted. It is foreseen that the options used will vary for each line of approach.

The core group, supervised by the Steering Committee, will initiate, coordinate and report on the aforementioned co-production activities.

The goal is to create support and consensus to develop and implement an Open Science Infrastructure.

5.2 COMMUNICATION AND TOOLS

COMMUNICATION TOOLS

- Webpage with information about SPII at the UNL-site
- [Zenodo](#) community with published documents from SPII
- Regular posts on LinkedIn

^a See for a stakeholders overview Appendix 3.

5.3 PLANNING

June							July							August							September							October							November							December							January							February						
23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13																				
Dev. reference model 0.2							Start conference July 1							Online consultation; other engagement activities							OSF sessions Oct 14							Further engagement activities							Report interim results							Publication interim results							Next steps conference Feb 10													

- The working methods to involve and connect to the stakeholders from the start conference onwards will have to be decided and developed in collaboration with the stakeholders. At the moment of writing the following is foreseen:
- Line [B]: an online consultation about reference model with feedback options and with regular updates of the reference model incorporating the comments is foreseen for July, August and September
- Line [C]: the koppelvlakken overleg will be continued with participation of SPII. Other collaboration methods with the other projects and infrastructures have to be discussed at the start conference.
- Line [A]: workshops and meetings with stakeholder communities are foreseen develop additional use cases.

6. SCOPE FOR 2026

For 2026, the scope of the programme is as follows:

- The primary focus is on the development of the reference model for open science infrastructure [line B].
- The lines A [additional use cases] and C [connecting and collaboration with infrastructures] will be used to inform and shape the reference model.
- Line D [organisational setup] will be taken up in November. At that time, the results of several other relevant projects about government models in relation to infrastructure are known. The proposal is to build on these results to create several models for the organisation and governance of the open science infrastructure.
- Line E is seen as relevant for the later stages of the development in 2027.

7. REFERENCES

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APPENDIX 1: WORKING METHOD FOR LINE B [IN DEVELOPMENT]

- An iterative process with:
 - A development group with software architects and IT-knowledgeable persons (n=6) that works out in steps elements of the reference model
 - A wider consultation of reviewers among stakeholders (especially the OSNL infrastructural projects and existing research infrastructures) that reviews each interim results proposed by the development group.
- Experiences and results from other countries will be included in the process: there are similar projects in Germany (NFDI), Finland and possibly other countries (see the references mentioned above).

A more detailed proposal for the working method (a small and lightweight subsection of HORA) is in development. The following prerequisites have been formulated:

- **Applicable:** The aim is to develop (parts of) a reference model that is quickly applicable. Keywords are interoperability (between the different blocks) and interoperability to solve the major bottlenecks and fulfil major needs. The idea is to connect blocks (see figure 1) and to create a layer above those blocks that supports the seamless workflows of the researchers. The focus of the reference model is on those connecting pieces that are actionable. ‘The bits that we can turn into action’.
- **Many stakeholders:** The reference model has to be relevant for many different parties. Every organization has its own timeline of IT-developments, so it must be possible to ‘get on board’ at different moments. In addition, the reference model must serve as a guideline for the development of the infrastructures by the various stakeholders.

The working method for line B is still under discussion. Below a sketch that will be worked out further.

Figure 6 Infrastructure landscape model

- Create as a first step an infrastructure landscape model, distinguishing between presentation layer, systems of engagement, systems of record, and systems of insights (see figure 6) and plotting infrastructures (existing and in development) in it.
- Regarding the systems of engagement:
 - Place the research project at the center
 - Identify data input and output per phase of a research project
 - Identify the key connections required
 - Describe these step-by-step, preferably with actionable development options with clear added value so that momentum is created for the next steps in the development process.

APPENDIX 2: PROPOSED WORKING METHOD FOR LINE C [IN DEVELOPMENT]

(1) Per project: Identify specific issues (connection points, pain points) within the user journey of your project that might be shared concerns (shared questions, shared issues) with other infrastructural projects

- Examples:
 - Access for specific users (outside universities, foreign users, etc.)
 - FAIR metadata
 - PIDS used
- Result: overview per project of shared issues as input for step (2)

(2) Workshop(s) with project leads:

- a. **What are shared concerns/challenges your project faces in terms of standards, capabilities and sustainability issues?**
- b. **How might Open Science infrastructure help in this regard?**

Example:

Category:	Standards	Capabilities	Sustainability issues
<i>Question:</i>	<i>How do you ensure that your output is understood by other modules??</i>	<i>Which functions are you currently building within the project that are actually more like 'general utilities'??</i>	<i>What happens to your results/data once the project funding has ended??</i>
Possibilities	FAIR metadata GDPR	Audit log	...
What could OSI offer?	Interoperability register/ common API-definition	PID-services Metadata catalogue	Potentially more chance of sustainability

Desired results of the workshop(s):

Step 1: Matrix

Projects	Standards	Capabilities	Sustainability
1			

2			
3			
..			

Step 2: Lego-check per project

- Input: which data/services does your infrastructure needs from other infrastructures or OSI?
- Output: What can your infrastructure deliver to other infrastructural components/OSI?
- Glue: which standards are used by your infrastructural component that others use as well ?

Step 3: Can we develop user journeys that overarch multiple infrastructural components with and without OSI?

APPENDIX 3: STAKEHOLDERS OVERVIEW

Below a sketch of an overview of the stakeholders that are important to SPII. Some are double mentioned:

- Participants/signatories in the Open Science Covenant (the Ministry of OCW and 15 institutes: NWO, UNL, NFI, VH, SURF, KNAW, NWO-I, ZonMw, UKB, KB, DANS, Netherlands eScience Center, 4TUResearchData, Health-RI and SHB)
- Universities:
 - UNL
 - Chiefs Open Science
 - Within universities:
 - ICT departments; software architects
 - Sectorraden/ decanenoverleg
 - Libraries; RDM and OA services
 - Data stewards/DCC's
- Universities of Applied Sciences
 - VH
 - DCC-PO
 - Within universities of Applied Sciences
 - ICT departments; software architects
 - Libraries; RDM and OA services
 - Data stewards
- KNAW
- NWO-I
- Data archives
 - DANS
 - 4TU.ResearchData
- National library organisations:
 - UKB:
 - Directors
 - working group 'Research Support'
 - SHB
 - Director/managers
 - Working group 'Open Scholarly Communications'
- TDCC's (LSH, NES, SSH)

- Open Science Community NL
- CS-NL (Citizen Science) and CS-hubs
- Research funders:
 - NWO:
 - OSNL:
 - OSNL-financed infrastructural projects:
 - GWI's
 - SIA
 - ZonMW
 - SIO
- EOSC-NL

APPENDIX 4: OVERVIEW OSNL INFRASTRUCTURAL PROJECTS

It is foreseen that a next version of the programme plan also includes TDCC and other relevant infrastructural projects.

Characterization ^b	Thematic focus	Project title	Lead institution
computing solution for astronomical datasets	NES	OSPREY: Open Science Platform for astRonomical discovery	ASTRON
Hardware	Generic	Open-source Hardware Infrastructure for The Netherlands (OSHNE)	Eindhoven University of Technology
Metadata	Generic	Scaling small in NL - Implementing a joint metadata management system to enable joint outputs and services in partnership with Open Access Book infrastructure services	University of Groningen
Metadata	Generic	BROCCOLI – the Dutch hub for healthy open research information	SURF
metadata voor research data	LSH	Retrospective FAIRification by complementation of metadata and interoperability (RetroFAIR)	LUMC
metadata voor research data	LSH	Open Science Data Infrastructure – strengthening FAIR principles in the Amsterdam Cohort Studies on HIV and other sexually transmitted infections	Amsterdam UMC
metadata voor research data	LSH	Medical Imaging Curation and Annotation Platform	Erasmus MC
metadata voor research data	NES	SPI-Birds Data Entry Software (SPI-BirDES): closing the FAIR data life cycle on the ecology of breeding birds	Netherlands Institute of Ecology
preregistration of research projects	NES/LSH	PRIOR project - PReregistration Integration and Optimization for animal Research	Amsterdam UMC
publication	Generic	National Open Access Books Platform	Huygens Institute
publication	Generic	UKB Publishing Browser – your scholarly communication decision aid	Wageningen University
publication	Generic	Infrastructures for Diamond Open Access in the Netherlands	Erasmus University
publication	Generic	DURF - Dutch Repository Federation	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
publication	Generic	Next-generation publishing: Advancing the publish-review-curate model	Leiden University
publication	SSH	PURE3D 2.0: Building a Sustainable and Open Infrastructure for 3D Scholarship	Maastricht University

^b The characterization is based on a short description of the project and might be incorrect.

research data management	Generic	Yoda as connecting infrastructure for seamless open science	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
research data repository	Generic	Project Hippocampus - A collaborative infrastructure for AI-Driven Science	Eindhoven University of Technology
research data repository	LSH	Growth fund Health-RI - Realisation of a national health infrastructure	Health-RI
research data repository	NES	An online open resource serving as a linking pin in mycology	Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute
research data repository	NES	Brightlands Open Data Hub: A 5-star linked-open data platform for interdisciplinary crop science research and education	Maastricht University
research data repository	NES	GeoFAIR: Optimizing use of high impact geoscientific data by linking to available international research infrastructure	Utrecht University
research data repository	SSH/LSH	Unified Governance for Availability, Access, and Usage of Socio-medical data - for researchers, health professionals, policymakers, and citizens	UMC Groningen
research data repository interoperability	NES/LSH	Schema-Driven Interoperability of Biomedical Data Resources for Improved Knowledge Dissemination and Reuse	Maastricht University
research data tool	Generic	OpenTwente - A stepping stone towards open innovation for and by Twente	Saxion
research data tool	Generic	Transforming Research Equipment Connectivity: An Open IoT Platform for Real-Time Data Collection and Digital Twinning	Wageningen University
research data tool	Generic	Collaborative Research Open Workspace for Networked data (CROWN)	Erasmus University
research data tool	Generic	ReproHub: Enhanced Replicability and Open Science Education for Research with Secondary and Sensitive Data	Tilburg University
research data tool	Generic	DigiLab Toegepaste Kennis	Deltares
research data tool	LSH	HealthMetaSyn: FAIR and Safe Synthetic Data from Health Record Metadata	UMC Utrecht
research data tool	LSH	Patient signalS United in a Metabase: the PLUM Platform	UMC Utrecht
research data tool	LSH	OPEN-MRH: An Open Science Platform and Novel Dataset to Address Medication Related Harm	Utrecht University
research data tool	LSH	Multimodal Monitoring of the Respiratory System: an integrated analysis platform (M3Resp)	University of Twente
research data tool	LSH	National Infrastructure for Ophthalmic Imaging	Erasmus MC
research data tool (citizen science)	NES	UTMOST - Utrecht Meteorological Open Science Testbed	Utrecht University
research tool	SSH	Voicing the Document: Using vision-language models to enhance our understanding of historical document collections	KNAW Humanities Cluster
research tool	SSH	Bridging the Digital Divide: Open, Scalable, and Accessible Software for Legal Data	Maastricht University
research tool	SSH	Observatory for Political Texts, Images and MultiMedia (OPTIMA)	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
research tool citizen science	SSH	Chains of the Past: Open Infrastructure for the Global History of Dutch Slavery and Slave Trade	Radboud University
software	Generic	An Open-Source Software Ecosystem for Causal Inference: Addressing Needs Across Research, Education, and Industry	Radboud University
software	Generic	Towards a community-driven and sustainable Research Software Directory	Netherlands eScience Center
software	Generic	Infra-Structural Equation Modelling: Sustainably Scaling an Indispensable Open-Source Theory-Testing Infrastructure	University of Amsterdam
software	SSH/LSH	Fast estimation of classical and new latent variable models in R	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

software library	NES	OPynSim: A python-native library for interoperable biomechanical simulations	Delft University of Technology
software library	NES	LoFAIR: FAIR Data & Open Software for LOFAR	ASTRON
software library	NES	The General Open Orbital Dynamics (GOOD) Platform	Delft University of Technology
software library	NES	Enabling FAIR for AI: Infrastructure for Transparency and Reproducibility of Research Software	Delft University of Technology
research data and software repository for Machine learning	Generic	OpenML Next: Building the Future of AI-driven Open Science	Eindhoven University of Technology